

VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF POLYMERIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

Albert H. CARDON

Faculty of Applied Sciences (CONT) - Free University Brussels (V.U.B.)
Pleinlaan 2, B-1050 Brussels (Belgium)

ABSTRACT

Even if by some specific stacking sequences the elastic nature of the fibers is introduced in different directions in a composite laminate, in order to obtain a global elastic behaviour the basic internal, and even global, viscoelastic behaviour induced by the polymer matrix will be present at any time. It is important to have some control of this time dependent behaviour for a safe design of a structural component for a give life time and some stated general, mechanical and environmental, loading history.

INTRODUCTION

In a unidirectionally reinforced polymer matrix composite with long continuous fibers, (such as glass, carbon or aramid fibers), the mechanical behaviour in the fiber direction is dominated by the fibers and can be considered as elastic or elasto-plastic. In any other direction, the influence of the polymer matrix and the properties of the interface region between fibers and matrix are important and the behaviour of the composite is viscoelastic with a linearity range function of the direction.

The unidirectional reinforced composite exhibits a strong anisotropic behaviour. The combination of this lamina with others, reinforced in different directions, gives a laminate with a "global" elastic behaviour but the viscoelasticity is still present, at least on three levels :

- under constant external loadings stress transfers occur not only between matrix and fibers in a lamina but also between lamina ;
- environmental conditions have significant influences on the mechanical behaviour of the matrix and on the properties of the interface region between fibres and matrix ;
- the global thermomechanical properties of the composite will change in function of time and and the prediction of their evolution is a central problem for safe design.

The analysis of the viscoelastic behaviour of the unidirectional reinforced lamina under transverse and off-axes loadings for different loading levels and different environmental conditions is the necessary basis for the mechanical characterisation of a laminate and a structural component.

VISCOELASTIC MODEL

In order to be able to describe test results in a general anisotropic situation, even out of the linearity domain, a constitutive formulation is necessary, simple enough in order to need a limited number of experimental results, and general enough in order to be compatible with the thermodynamic principles.

The single integral formulation proposed by R. Schapery, [1-3], is very convenient for the analysis of the general viscoelastic behaviour of polymer matrix composites.

The general Schapery model can be written :

$$n_a = - \frac{\partial G_R}{\partial F_a} + \frac{\partial \hat{F}_q}{\partial F_a} \int_{-\infty}^{\psi} \Delta S_{qr} (\psi - \psi') \frac{d[\hat{F}_r/a_G]}{d\psi'} d\psi' \quad (1)$$

where n_a : generalised coordinates

F_a : associated generalised forces

\hat{F}_q : functions of the generalised forces

ψ : reduced time $d\psi = dt/a_\sigma$ and $a_\sigma = a_D/a_G$

(a_D : common factor of the n_q terms ; a_G : common factor of the n_q terms).

$$\Delta S_{qr} = \sum_p \frac{d^r_{pq} d^r_{pr}}{d^r_p} (1 - e^{-(\psi - \psi')/r_p})$$

G_R : Gibbs free energy in the reference state.

For the one-dimensional case (1) reduces to :

$$\epsilon = g_0 S_0 \sigma + g_1 \int_{-\infty}^{\psi} \Delta S (\psi - \psi') \frac{d[g_2 \sigma]}{d\psi'} d\psi' \quad (2)$$

In the expression (2) we have 4 nonlinearising functions : g_0 , g_1 , g_2 and a_σ .

If $g_0 = g_1 = g_2 = a_\sigma = 1$ the nonlinear equation (2) reduces to the classical linear viscoelastic constitutive equation.

The nonlinearising functions may be dependent from the stress level or stress state, from the temperature and other environmental conditions.

VISCOELASTIC CHARACTERISATION

From the master curve by curve fitting the different "linear" parts of (2) can be obtained. Afterwards from creep and creep recovery tests the nonlinearising function can be obtained.

The Schapery model was used by H. Brinson and co-workers for the analysis of thermoset matrix unidirectionally reinforced composites, [4-8]. Further systematic development for the use of Schapery's model was done by C. Hiel, [9]. The application of the model for biaxial stress states was developed by R. Brouwer, [10]. The applicability of the Schapery model, and the procedures developed by H. Brinson and co-workers, C. Hiel and R. Brouwer, for thermoplastic matrix composites was investigated by X. Xiao, [11].

Tests must be carried out in order to obtain the linearity range of any of the nonlinearising functions for variations of the different significant parameters.

Some of these parameters can be used as accelerating factors for the analysis of long term behaviour of lamina, laminate and structure, starting from short term tests by application of a generalised time stress temperature superposition principle as proposed and applied by H. Brinson and co-workers.

For a unidirectionally reinforced composite these tests must be done under transverse tensile conditions and under shear conditions such as those obtained by off-axes testing.

The viscoelastic characterisation gives us the evolution of the thermomechanical characteristics of the unidirectional reinforced lamina.

Classical laminate programs can predict the compliance evolution of laminate and structure for a given time limit. Design codes can use this limit values within a classical elastic program.

It is probably more easy to handle the nonlinear behaviour in the prediction of the compliance evolution than to use a nonlinear viscoelastic behaviour in the design program.

APPLICATIONS - EXAMPLES

Figure 1 shows a typical creep curve and creep recovery curve for a $[60]_{8S}$ of T300/934 at 160°C and $0.72 \sigma_r$ as given in [9].

Fig. 1

Figures 2 (a-d) give the evolution of the 4 nonlinearising function in the shear mode obtained on T300/934, $[10]_{8S}$ as given in [9].

Fig. 2.a

Fig. 2.b

Fig. 2.c

Fig. 2.d

Figures 3 (a-b) give the shear compliance of $[10]_{8S}$, T300/934 at 149°C and 168°C for different stress levels as given in [9].

Fig. 3.a (D66)

Fig. 3.b (D66)

Figures 4 (a-b) give the creep and creep recovery results obtained on APC 2 for transverse tensile at 97°C (a) and for 15 degrees off-axis test at 91°C (b) as given in [11].

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4

Finally figure 5 gives the shear compliance of APC-2 as function of time and shear stress level as given in [11].

Fig. 5

CONCLUSION

By using the nonlinear viscoelastic model proposed by Schapery, it is possible to obtain the time evolution of the different moduli from short term tests. In combination with some long term prediction methods, such as those proposed by Brinson and co-workers, e.g. [8], an analysis of the long term behaviour of laminates can be performed. Real time testing must be done on a systematic coordinated basis in the future.

It is also necessary to study the coupling of the viscoelastic behaviour with fatigue behaviour and even with impact behaviour in order to have a complete information on long term behaviour under general loading conditions.

REFERENCES

- [1] R.A. SCHAPERY (1964), "Application of Thermodynamics to Thermomechanical, Fracture and Birefringent Phenomena in Viscoelastic Media", *Journal of Applied Physics* vol. 35, 5, pp. 1451-1465.
- [2] R.A. SCHAPERY (1966), "A Theory of Nonlinear Thermoviscoelasticity based on Irreversible Thermodynamics", *Proc. 5th US. National Congress on Applied Mechanics*, ASME, pp. 511-530.
- [3] R.A. SCHAPERY (1968), "On a Thermodynamic Constitutive Theory and its Applications to various Nonlinear Materials", *Thermoinelasticity* (ed. Boley), Springer Verlag, Wien - New York (1970), pp. 259-285
- [4] H.F. BRINSON (1981), "Experimental Mechanics Applied to the Accelerated Characterization of Polymer based Composites", *New Trends in Experimental Mechanics* (Ed. J.T. Pindera), Springer Verlag, Vienna, pp. 1-69.
- [5] H.F. BRINSON and D.A. DILLARD (1982), "The Prediction of Long Term Viscoelastic Properties of Fiber Reinforced Plastics", *Proc. ICCM IV, Tokyo*.
- [6] C.C. HIEL, A.H. CARDON and H.F. BRINSON (1984), "The Nonlinear Viscoelastic Response of Resin Matrix Composite Laminates", *NASA Contractor Report 3772*, July 1984.
- [7] H.F. BRINSON (1985), "Viscoelastic Behaviour and Lifetime (Durability) Predictions", *Mechanical Characterisation of Load Bearing Fibre Composite Laminates* (ed. A.H. Cardon - G. Verchery), Elsevier Appl. Sc. Publ., London, pp. 3-20.
- [8] M.E. TUTTLE and H.F. BRINSON (1986), "Prediction of the Long Term Creep Compliance of General Composite Laminates", *Experimental Mechanics*, March 1986, pp. 89-102.
- [9] C.C. HIEL, "The Nonlinear Viscoelastic Response of Resin Matrix Composite Materials", *Doctoral thesis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel*, 1983.
- [10] R. BROUWER, "Nonlinear Viscoelastic Characterization of Transversely Isotropic Fibrous Composites under Biaxial Loading", *Doctoral thesis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel*, 1986.
- [11] X. XIAO, "Viscoelastic Characterization of Thermoplastic Matrix Composites", *Doctoral thesis, Vrije Universiteit Brussel*, 1987.